

Synthesis and spectral studies of chromium(III) and iron(III) complexes of trioxadiazamacrocycles

R. N. Prasad*, Sarita Chaudhary and Amita Jain

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 055, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : rnp_1949@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 12 October 2011, revised 12 February 2012, accepted 13 February 2013

Abstract : 1+1 Cyclocondensation of 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenylpropane-1,2-dione and benzil in the presence of Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} as templates afforded macrocyclic complexes of the type [ML(NO₃)](NO₃)₂ (M = Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and L = 17-membered trioxadiazamacrocycle). These complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductances, magnetic moments, electronic, IR and FAB mass spectral studies. The complexes have been screened for their antibacterial activities against several species of bacteria.

Keywords : Trioxadiazamacrocycles, iron(III) complexes, chromium(III) complexes, magnetic moments, IR spectra, FAB mass spectra.

Introduction

Transition metal complexes of macrocycles have been of considerable interest in terms of structural chemistry and biological function¹. Oxa-azamacrocycles are efficient complexing agents for a variety of transition and heavy metal cations²⁻⁴. Recognition of the importance of complexes containing oxa-azamacrocyclic ligands leads to considerable efforts directed towards the development of reliable synthesis of these interesting and important compounds. Fe^{III} and Fe^{II} complexes of N₃O₂ macrocycles derived from 2,6-diacetylpyridine and 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane have been reported by Drew *et al.*⁵. Nelson *et al.*⁶ have synthesized Fe^{II} and Co^{II} complexes of oxa-azamacrocycles derived from 2,6-diacetylpyridine and tetrafunctional diprimary amine. The use of oxa-azamacrocycles as sensors for cations, anions and molecular scaffolds for materials and biological models has prompted us to investigate the chemistry of the macrocycles containing N₂O₃ donor systems⁷⁻¹¹. We report herein the synthesis and characterization of Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes of 17-membered oxa-azamacrocycles derived from α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione or benzil and 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane.

Results and discussion

Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes (I) of trioxa-diazamacrocycles have been obtained by 1 : 1 : 1 molar reactions of metal salts with 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione or benzil (Scheme 1). The resulting macrocyclic complexes are coloured solids, which are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as methanol, chloroform, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide etc. but are soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide. These are stable at room temperature but decompose at 225–255 °C. The elemental analyses of the complexes confirm their stoichiometry (Table 1). Molar conductances of the complexes in DMSO lie in the range 62–87 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ suggesting them to be 1 : 2 electrolytes with ionization of two nitrate groups¹². The μ_{eff} values for Cr^{III} complexes (Table 1) are in the range 3.91–4.26 B.M., which correspond to three unpaired electrons¹³. The μ_{eff} values for Fe^{III} complexes (5.88–6.12 B.M.) are consistent with high spin d^5 system^{14,15}.

Electronic spectra :

Electronic spectra of Cr^{III} complexes of macrocycles show three bands in the region 16775–17220, 23320–25495 and 25995–28975 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to

M	R ¹	R ²	
(1a) Cr	(1b) Fe	CH ₃	CH ₃
(2a) Cr	(2b) Fe	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅
(3a) Cr	(3b) Fe	CH ₃	C ₃ H ₇
(4a) Cr	(4b) Fe	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅
(5a) Cr	(5b) Fe	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅
(6a) Cr	(6b) Fe	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes.

${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4B_{2g}$ and ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ transitions respectively¹⁶. The positions of these bands are consistent with distorted octahedral geometry of chromium(III) complexes. Electronic spectra of Fe^{III} complexes of oxazamacrocycles show three bands. The bands at ~ 13604 cm^{-1} and in the region 16848 – 17102 cm^{-1} may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ transitions respectively¹⁷. Intense bands in the region 28775 – 30397 cm^{-1} are assigned to ligand to metal charge transfer⁵.

Infrared spectra :

None of the complexes exhibits bands at ~ 1700 cm^{-1} and 3200 – 3400 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra which could be ascribed to uncoordinated $>C=O$ or $-NH_2$ groups¹⁸. In the mononuclear Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Co^{III} and Ni^{II} complexes of an N₆O₄ macrocycle⁶ derived from 2,6-diacetylpyridine and 2-methoxyethylene and Fe^{III}, Fe^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes of a 15-membered N₃O₂ macrocycle⁵ derived from

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of the macrocyclic complexes

Compds.	Complex	Colour and Dec. temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analyses (%) :		μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Molar cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)
				Found	(Calcd.)		
				Metal	N		
1a	[Cr{(Me) ₂ [17]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) ₂	Green (250)	52	10.11 (10.23)	5.47 (5.50)	3.98	85
2a	[Cr{(Me)(Et)[17]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) ₂	Green (230)	40	9.88 (9.96)	5.34 (5.36)	4.12	82
3a	[Cr{(Me)(Pr)[17]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) ₂	Green (245)	47	9.65 (9.70)	5.17 (5.22)	4.17	72
4a	[Cr{(Et) ₂ [17]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) ₂	Green (245)	58	9.66 (9.70)	5.32 (5.22)	3.91	66
5a	[Cr{(Me)(Ph)[17]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) ₂	Green (230)	51	9.00 (9.12)	4.84 (4.91)	4.26	65
6a	[Cr{(Ph) ₂ [17]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) ₂	Green (242)	53	8.32 (8.22)	4.38 (4.43)	3.96	74
1b	[Fe{(Me) ₂ [17]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) ₂	Brown (242)	47	11.66 (10.76)	5.44 (5.47)	5.93	78
2b	[Fe{(Me)(Et)[17]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) ₂	Brown (255)	48	10.50 (10.47)	5.38 (5.33)	6.09	62
3b	[Fe{(Me)(Pr)[17]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) ₂	Brown (240)	45	10.13 (10.20)	5.17 (5.19)	5.90	74
4b	[Fe{(Et) ₂ [17]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) ₂	Brown (240)	40	10.15 (10.20)	5.12 (5.19)	6.01	65
5b	[Fe{(Me)(Ph)[17]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) ₂	Brown (225)	37	9.65 (9.59)	4.81 (4.88)	6.12	86
6b	[Fe{(Ph) ₂ [17]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) ₂	Brown (225)	36	8.72 (8.66)	4.36 (4.40)	5.91	81

2,6-diacetylpyridine and 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane absence of absorption bands at 1700 and 3100–3300 cm^{-1} which could be attributed to the unreacted carbonyl or primary amine groups has been reported. All the complexes show medium to strong intensity bands in the region 1590–1620 cm^{-1} attributable to the coordinated $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ resulting through the condensation of $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups of α -diketones with $-\text{NH}_2$ groups of the aliphatic diamines¹⁹. In the IR spectra of Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes of macrocycles derived from carbohydrazide and 2,6-diacetylpyridine absorption bands at 1580–1640 cm^{-1} have been assigned to $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ ¹⁶. Nitrate complexes show bands in the region 1370–1400 and 805–820 cm^{-1} due to ionic nitrate and bands at 1020–1035 cm^{-1} can be assigned to coordinated nitrate groups²⁰. Appearance of bands at 1460–1540 cm^{-1} confirms the monodentate coordination mode of the nitrate group²¹.

FAB mass spectra :

The FAB mass spectra of three complexes $[\text{Cr}\{\text{Me}\}(\text{Et})[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{NO}_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$, $[\text{Cr}\{\text{Me}\}(\text{Pr})[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{NO}_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $[\text{Fe}\{\text{Me}\}(\text{Et})[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{NO}_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$ have been recorded using NBA matrix. Peaks at m/z 136, 137, 154, 289 and 307 are due to the matrix. The spectra have been analysed on the basis of isotopic abundances of different nuclei. The complexes show the peaks corresponding to molecular ions $[\text{M}^+]$ and free macrocycles $[\text{L}^+]$ which confirms the formation of the macrocyclic complexes. Cook *et al.*²² observed the peak corresponding to the macrocycle in the mass spectra of the complex of the macrocycle derived from furan-2,5-dicarbaldehyde and 3,6,9-trioxaundecane-1,11-diamine. In addition to the peaks due to the molecular ions and the macrocycles, the spectra exhibit peaks assignable to various fragments arising from the thermal cleavage of the macrocycles and their complexes. The fragmentation pattern for the complex $[\text{Cr}\{\text{Me}\}(\text{Et})[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{NO}_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$ is given in Scheme 2. The complex exhibits a molecular ion $[\text{M}^+]$ peak at m/z 522 (8.3%). Fragment **b** is formed due to the loss of three nitrates from molecular ion **a** and appears at m/z 336 (22.22%). There are two possible pathways for the fragmentation of the complex :

[A] In this pathway the metal ion remains attached with the macrocyclic frame work and step by step loss of

CH_3 , CH_2 and CH_3 groups from **b** gives peaks at m/z 321 (2.7%), 307 (4.1%) and 292 (16.9%) due to species **c**, **d** and **e** respectively. Loss of chromium atom from the species **e** finally gives the species **i** at m/z 240 (2.7%).

[B] In this pathway the metal ion may be lost from the macrocyclic complex in the beginning and a peak at m/z 284 (16.6%) appears due to the free macrocycle **f**. Subsequent loss of CH_3 , CH_2 and CH_3 groups from the macrocycle gives peaks at m/z 269 (2.9%), 255 (2.7%) and 240 (2.7%) due to the species **g**, **h** and **i** respectively²³.

Antibacterial activities :

The data for the antibacterial activities of the compounds against various bacteria have been recorded in Table 2. The results point out that the compounds are inhibiting the growth of bacteria to a greater extent²⁴. Mode of action of antimicrobials may involve various targets in microorganisms, e.g. interference with the cell wall synthesis, damage to the cytoplasmic membrane as a result of which cell permeability may be altered or they may disorganize the lipoprotein leading to the cell death. Such activity of the metal chelates can be explained on the basis of Overtone's concept and Tweedy's chelation theory²⁵.

Experimental

$\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fluka) and $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fluka) were of A.R. grade. 1,13-Diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (Merck), 2,3-pentanedione (Fluka), 2,3-hexanedione (Merck), 3,4-hexanedione (Aldrich), 1-phenyl propane-1,2-dione (Aldrich) and benzil (Sisco, India) were used as supplied and biacetyl (Aldrich) and *n*-butanol (Merck) were distilled before use. Cr and Fe were determined by standard methods²⁶. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets in the region 400–4000 cm^{-1} on a Shimadzu 8400 S spectrophotometer. Conductances in DMSO were determined using Systronics Direct Reading Conductivity Meter-304. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes :

To the butanolic solution of $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.940 g, 2.0 mmol in ~15 ml of *n*-butanol), a solution of 2,3-

Scheme 2. Fragmentation pattern of $[\text{Cr}\{(\text{Me})(\text{Et})[17]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}(\text{NO}_3)(\text{NO}_3)_2]$.

Table 2. m/z values and % relative intensity of important peaks in FAB mass spectra of Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes

Fragments ^a	Comps.		
	$[\text{Cr}\{(\text{Me})(\text{Et})[17]\text{diene-N}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{NO}_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$	$[\text{Cr}\{(\text{Me})(\text{Pr})[17]\text{diene-N}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{NO}_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$	$[\text{Fe}\{(\text{Me})(\text{Et})[17]\text{diene-N}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{NO}_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$
$[\text{M}]^+$	522 (8.3%)	526 (13.15%)	536 (9.4%)
$[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$	523 (6.9%)	527 (7.14%)	537 (6.5%)
$[\text{M}-3\text{NO}_3]^+$	336 (22.22%)	340 (2.6%)	350 (21.52%)
$[\text{L}]^+$	284 (16.6%)	284 (4.7%)	298 (17.52%)
$[\text{L}-\text{CH}_3]^+$	269 (2.9%)	269	283 (3.2%)
$[\text{L}-\text{CH}_3-\text{CH}_2]^+$	255 (2.7%)	255 (2.6%)	269 (1.5%)
$[\text{L}-2\text{CH}_3-\text{CH}_2]^+$	240 (2.7%)	240	254 (1.7%)
$[\text{L}-2\text{CH}_3-2\text{CH}_2]^+$	-	-	240 (5.3%)
$[\text{M}-3\text{NO}_3-\text{CH}_3]^+$	321 (2.7%)	325	335 (3.3%)
$[\text{M}-3\text{NO}_3-\text{CH}_3-\text{CH}_2]^+$	307 (4.1%)	311 (4.7%)	321 (4.3%)
$[\text{M}-3\text{NO}_3-2\text{CH}_3-\text{CH}_2]^+$	292 (6.9%)	296	306 (4.2%)
$[\text{M}-3\text{NO}_3-2\text{CH}_3-2\text{CH}_2]^+$	-	-	292 (6.3%)

^aAll fragments are uni-positive ions.

Note

Table 3. Antibacterial screening data of the complexes

Comps.	Inhibition (mm) after 24 h (conc. in ppm)		
	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (-)	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i> (-)	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (-)
1a	24	10	16
2a	18	21	9
3a	7	9	7
4a	11	19	15
5a	14	23	18
6a	6	19	4
1b	15	7	13
2b	19	9	7
3b	18	11	18
4b	6	18	15
5b	11	7	8
6b	10	9	18

butanedione (0.202 g, 2.0 mmol in ~15 ml *n*-butanol) was added dropwise with constant stirring. 1,13-Diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (0.517 g, 2 mmol in ~15 ml in *n*-butanol) was then added dropwise with constant stirring which was continued for ~5 h. Then it was refluxed for ~4 h. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the corresponding Fe^{III} complex was synthesized. Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes of other macrocycles derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenylpropane-1,2-dione or benzil were also synthesized in a similar manner.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, for facilities and the Head, CDRI, Lucknow for FAB mass spectra.

References

1. P. Zanello, R. Seeber, A. Cinquantini, G. Mazzocchin and L. Fabbrizzi, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1982, 893.
2. R. M. Izatt, J. S. Bradshaw, S. A. Nielsen, J. D. Lamb and J. J. Christensen, *Chem. Rev.*, 1985, **85**, 271.
3. K. E. Krakowiak, J. S. Bradshaw and D. J. Z. Krakowiak, *Chem. Rev.*, 1989, **89**, 929.

4. R. M. Izatt, K. Pawlak, J. S. Bradshaw and R. L. Bruening, *Chem. Rev.*, 1991, **91**, 1721.
5. M. G. B. Drew, A. H. Bin Othman, S. G. Mcfall, P. A. D. McIlroy and S. M. Nelson, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 1173.
6. S. M. Nelson, M. McCann, C. Stevenson and M. G. B. Drew, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1979, 1477.
7. G. W. Gokel, W. M. Leevy and M. E. Weber, *Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **104**, 2723.
8. V. Bernhardt and G. A. Lawrance, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **104**, 297.
9. K. P. Wainwright, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1997, **166**, 35.
10. J. M. Lehn, "Supramol. Chem"., VCH, New York, 1995.
11. L. F. Lindoy, "The Chemistry of Macrocyclic Ligand Complexes", Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1989.
12. J. Lewis and T. D. O. Donoghue, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1980, 736.
13. T. A. Khan, S. S. Hasan, N. Jahan and S. I. Khan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 450.
14. S. K. Gupta and Y. S. Kushwah, *Polyhedron*, 2001, **20**, 2019.
15. M. G. B. Drew, A. H. Bin Othman, P. D. A. McIlroy and S. M. Nelson, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 2507.
16. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
17. R. Saraswat and V. B. Rana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 493.
18. R. Saraswat, S. Singh and V. B. Rana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 478.
19. W. U. Malik, R. Bembi, R. Singh, S. P. Taneja and D. Raj, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **68**, 223.
20. A. Walker and J. R. Ferraro, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **43**, 2689.
21. M. C. Rakowski, M. Rycheck and D. H. Busch, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 1194.
22. D. H. Cook and D. E. Fenton, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1979, 810.
23. Z. A. Siddiqi and M. M. Khan, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2004, **34**, 897.
24. S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2005, **30**, 630.
25. B. G. Tweedy, *Phytopathology*, 1964, **55**, 910.
26. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., Longman, London, 1961.

